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INSIGHTS INTO HACK ATTACKS ON SMART GRID & THE USA FRAMEWORK AUSTRIAN EU PRESIDENCY CONFERENCE CYBER SECURITY IN THE ENERGY SECTOR

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INSIGHTS INTO HACK ATTACKS ON SMART GRID & THE USA FRAMEWORK

AUSTRIAN EU PRESIDENCY CONFERENCE CYBER SECURITY IN THE ENERGY SECTOR

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11 OCTOBER 2018

BIOGRAPHY

- Cyber warfare incident management and advisement
- Critical infrastructure security expert: Oil & Gas, Water, Electric & Nuclear
- Author, presenter at Black Hat, Security BSides, ICS/SCADA Nuclear Cyber Security
- Previous headed Aramco Overseas Security Operations, Information Protection & Intelligence
- Previous U.S Air Force Space Command
- Previous script kiddie hacking the US Government

US SMART GRID FRAMEWORK INTRODUCTION

- Bi-directional
- Resilient
- Near real-time data collection
- Encryption
- Interoperable
- Load Shedding
- Increased efficiency

SMART GRID COMPONENTS & TECHNOLOGIES

- On-demand
- Renewables
- Electric transport
- Smart appliances
- Auto Load-balancing
- Sub stations
- Smart homes
- Smart buildings
- Smart cities

DO YOU WANT HACKERS

**BECAUSE THATS
HOW YOU GET HACKERS**

SECURITY & PRIVACY CHALLENGES

Large number
of access points

Renewable
energy systems
entry points

Electricity theft

Most equipment
privately owned

Lacking
standisation

Security an
afterthought

LOGIC CONTROLLERS PLC

- Programmable
- Provides the logic for automation
- High value target
- Stuxnet
- Weak Link

80.http.get.body: Portal/Portal.mwsl

80.http.get.title: SIMATIC 300

```
"80": {
  "http": {
    "get": {
      "body": "<!DOCTYPE HTML PUBLIC "-//W3C//DTD HTML 4.01 Tr
\n  <title>\r\n    SIMATIC 300(1)\r\n  </title>\r\n  <MET
<body>\r\n    <a href=\"/_INTERNAL_Portal/Portal.mwsl?M
```

SOLAR & WIND

- Crucial for the Paris Accord
- Load management
- Climate change
- Many vendors
- Not much security testing

metadata.device_type: "solar panel"

IPv4 Hosts

Page: 1/3,519 Results: 87,974 Time: 160ms

 [77.243.63.16](#)

 Aalborg, North Denmark, Denmark

 443/https, 80/http

 www.mywindturbine.com

 80.http.get.body: a **wind turbine** . myWindTurbine

IPv4 Hosts

Page: 1/27 Results: 651 Time: 695ms

 [37.80.48.242](#)

 Germany

 502/modbus

 metadata.description: Solar Log **Solar Panel**

SCADA

SOLAR PANEL

Tag:

651 scada
651 solar panel
622 modbus
358 http
248 ftp
49 ssh
29 building control
29 fox
25 https
17 NPM
13 NPM6
10 JACE
10 JACE-7
9 embedded
8 telnet
4 NPM2
3 dns
2 database
2 mssql
1 bacnet

 Less

SMART ELECTRIC METERS

- Mandatory in some EU countries
- Mandatory in some US areas
- Privacy concerns
 - Can be refused in NL
- Security concerns
- No cyber security testing requirements

SMART ELECTRIC METERS

- Mandatory in some EU countries

4 Hosts 80.http.get.title: meternet

Results Map Metadata Report Docs

IPv4 Hosts
Page: 1/1 Results: 9 Time: 119ms

213.17.149.243 (213-17-149-243.static.ip.netia.com.pl)

- AS-NETIA Warszawa 02-822 (12741) Poland
- 21/ftp, 80/http
- MeterNET

80.http.get.body: <!DOCTYPE html> <html xmlns="http://www.w3.org/1999/xhtml" x-ng-cloak="" x-ng-app="login

http://.../login 2.44s

MeterNET **PRO**

Zaloguj się

Użytkownik

Hasło

Zapamiętaj mnie

Zaloguj

«F&F»

Energy consumption report		
Counter	Description 1	Description 2
meter-1		

OPEN AUTOMATED DEMAND RESPONSE

- North America
- Interoperability management
- Pricing
- Demand
- Controls all components
- Zero security

IPv4 Hosts

Page: 1/3 Results: 75 Time: 138ms

52 [redacted]

MICROSOFT-CORP-MSN-AS-BLOCK - Microsoft Corporation ([redacted]) Québec, Quebec, Canada
443/https
hydroquebecvtn.openadr.com
443.https.tls.certificate.parsed.issuer.organization: OpenADR Alliance

Tag:

58 https
52 http
27 ssh
3 ftp
1 DSL/cable modem
1 database
1 embedded
1 mysql
1 postgres
1 smtp

Chrome TLS Handshake

Version TLSv1.0

Cipher Suite TLS_RSA_WITH_AES_256_CBC_SHA (0x0035)

Trusted False : x509: certificate signed by unknown authority

MUAHAHAHA

CAN I HACK A HOUSE?

- Smart Appliances
- Washing Machines
- Refrigerators
- Smart plugs
- Smart lighting
- Smart House

80/HTTP

GET /

DETAILS

GO

Status Line 200 OK

Page Title Miele@home

GET / [view page]

HACK A HOUSE?

• Smart Appliances

Mach

tors

gs

nting

use

Miele@home Gateway XGW 3000

[Gateway Einstellungen](#)
[Gateway Administration](#)

[Miele@home Geräteübersicht](#)
[Miele@home Appliances Overview](#)

Miele
IMMER BESSER

 přihlášení

uživatel

heslo

přihlásit

NO GIMMICKS.
REAL SMART HOMES.

Loxone Web Interface

Connect

CA

- Sn
- W
- Re
- Sn
- Sn
- Sn

Country Breakdown

Country	Hosts	Frequency
France	12,099	90.74%
Germany	504	3.78%
Italy	347	2.6%
Netherlands	97	0.73%
Greece	55	0.41%
Switzerland	46	0.34%
Belgium	38	0.28%
Guadeloupe	22	0.16%
Morocco	20	0.15%
Austria	16	0.12%

Figure 108 Censys Alarm System Country Breakdown

13 days later

**Your strategic supply is gone!
GAMEOVER**

CONCLUSION

- Proactivity
- Security testing
- Don't assume its okay
- Connect after assessment
- Prepare for attack

QUESTIONS & THANK YOU

- Everything@hypasec.com
- [@SecEvangelism](#) & [@iiyonite](#)
- Hack the World with OSINT
- Down the Rabbit Hole an OSINT Journey
- Darknet Diaries Shamoon episode 30
- *When the internet gives you remotely exploitable systems, take them. They're like free candy, right?*

- Chris Kubecka